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**Annual Intermediate
Doctoral Discussions**

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Introduction

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Doctoral research: Mapping research futures

Doctoral research often functions as an early radar for emerging concerns within a discipline (Lazurko et al., 2020). Unlike more established researchers, who tend to consolidate existing paradigms, doctoral projects often explore uncertain intellectual terrain, crystallising questions that are still evolving rather than offering definitive answers. They are also intertwined with the uncertainties of early academic careers, reflecting the exploratory curiosity that characterises researchers whose identities and research programmes are still in formation (Başak & Thomas, 2014). The collection of studies presented in this Book of Abstracts illustrates precisely such a moment: a constellation of research inquiries that, taken together, outline the contours of contemporary debates in educational research while remaining open to transformation as the projects develop.

The projects included in this collection span topics from doctoral education and teacher formation to community partnerships (De Vido, Boscaini, Liu), social justice and inclusion in education (El Bouhali, Baisishta) digital technologies and media education (Marcato, Schmidt, Haq), youth and childhood educational practices cultures (Li, Zoroaster), and nonetheless, educational journeys and contexts in adulthood (Khosa, Boscaini, Slaviero, Bottaro, Elardo).

Also, across the projects, several shared themes and research questions become visible. At their core lies a broad concern with the transformation of educational systems and practices in conditions of social, technological, and institutional change.

First, many contributions address the problem of equity and access within educational institutions. Whether examining the experiences of international doctoral candidates (Khosa), the preparation of future teachers for inclusive classrooms (Baishistha), or the persistence of early school leaving and the role of second-chance educational environments (Boscaini), these studies interrogate how educational systems distribute recognition, opportunities, and resources. The work resonates with long-standing sociological analyses of education as a field structured by unequal forms of capital and recognition (Bourdieu, 1986). At the same time, it reflects contemporary debates about inclusion, belonging, and institutional fairness in global education contexts (Giroux, 2020).

Second, several projects investigate the role of teachers and educators as agents of educational transformation. Research on technological teacher identity (Marcato), the disaffection experienced by future educators within contemporary higher education systems (Elardo), peer feedback practices in early childhood education (Zoroaster), and new models of student participation in assessment (Slaviero) highlights the importance of professional agency in shaping learning environments. In this sense, teachers are not simply implementers of policy or curriculum but central actors in the co-construction of educational change. The prominence of teacher education within the doctoral landscape reflects a broader shift in educational research toward understanding teaching as a complex professional practice situated within evolving technological and social conditions: **in the spirit of these young researchers, teacher education should become a means of transforming educators into emancipatory intellectuals (Giroux, 2018), capable of facing the challenges posed by digital innovation, scientific development, and the conflicting interests of the global landscape.** This strand also characterises a well-established tradition in adult education and professional learning within the Academic Board (and hence the curriculum) of our PhD Programme.

Third, a number of studies emphasise the relational and ecological dimensions of education, focusing on connections between schools, communities, families, and territorial contexts. Research on educational communities in linguistically and culturally complex environments (El Bouhali), university–territory collaborations and social innovation processes (De Vido), and family–kindergarten partnerships in intercultural early childhood education (Liu) conceptualises education not as an isolated institutional process but as a network of interactions across social systems. Such perspectives echo ecological approaches to human development (Bronfenbrenner, 1979) and more recent work on educational ecosystems and social innovation. With several members in our academic group devoting their work to the liminal space between the schooling system and families, this is more than a resounding note: it is the emerging future generation heralding this relevant area of social pedagogy.

Alongside these central themes, additional lines of inquiry emerge around digital technologies and artificial intelligence in learning, student development and identity formation, and cultural narratives shaping educational meaning-making. Research on generative AI in personalised learning environments within corporate training (Schmidt), the educational implications of problematic smartphone use (Ul Haq), and the development of soft skills and reflective identity in higher education (Bottaro) reflects the growing presence of digital infrastructures and new forms of professional competence in educational contexts. At the same time, more humanistic lines of inquiry explore how cultural artefacts such as children’s picturebooks function as resources for navigating uncertainty and cultivating hope in complex social contexts (Chang Li).

Hidden Patterns in the Research Landscape

When the projects are examined collectively, several patterns become visible that may not be immediately apparent within individual studies. Perhaps most striking is that, despite the increasing visibility of digital technologies in educational discourse, the doctoral research agenda remains primarily oriented toward social and pedagogical transformation rather than

technological innovation itself. Technology appears as a contextual factor that shapes educational practice, as seen in studies of AI-supported learning environments (Schmidt) or digital media use among students (Ul-Haq). It acknowledges professional agency, praxis and ethics (Marcato) as part of a complex postdigital future. However, the direction towards the educational technologies' studies might expand into community engagement, where technology meets critical, social and inclusive pedagogies (Selwyn & CSET Collective, 2025).

A second pattern concerns the strong presence of community-oriented perspectives. Many projects explore educational processes that extend beyond formal institutions, involving families, communities, and local networks (El Bouhali; De Vido; Liu). This orientation suggests an understanding of education as embedded within broader social ecosystems rather than confined to the boundaries of schools or universities.

A third pattern relates to the role of uncertainty and experimentation in early-stage research. Doctoral projects frequently operate at the frontier between established theoretical traditions and emerging empirical concerns. As such, they often generate exploratory frameworks and conceptual models that may evolve significantly over the course of the research process. The projects collected here reflect this dynamic intellectual condition: rather than presenting definitive theoretical settlements, they propose questions, tentative frameworks, and methodological experiments. Particularly, they engage with interventionist methods and transformational aspirations attached to educational research. However, there are relevant methodological innovations connected to the usage of participatory and emancipatory methods, as well as techniques that adopt data-driven procedures and inductive quantitative analysis.

Let us say here that the value of doctoral research lies precisely in this provisional character. As the Royal Society has long emphasised, scientific inquiry depends on the open exchange of ideas that are still in formation. In its reflections on the nature of scientific progress, the Society famously adopted the motto *Nullius in verba*—"take nobody's word for it"—a reminder that knowledge advances through continuous questioning and critical dialogue rather than through the authority of established claims. As Robert Merton later observed, the ethos of science is sustained by norms that encourage scepticism, communal debate, and the testing of emerging ideas (Merton, 1973). In educational research, though, we cannot forget what was beautifully said by Donna Haraway: "all knowledge is situated", that is, emerging from specific positions, relations, and practices rather than from an abstract view from nowhere (Haraway, 1988). Scientific inquiry, in this sense, progresses not only through scepticism and debate, but also through the collective articulation of perspectives that remain open to revision, dialogue, and transformation.

Within this context, doctoral research in education can be understood as a space where incomplete ideas begin to crystallise into research trajectories. Some frameworks proposed in these studies may be refined, revised, or even abandoned as empirical work progresses. Others may develop into more robust conceptual contributions or **interesting innovative educational practices that can be applied in concrete educational and school contexts**. What

matters at this stage is the articulation of questions capable of sustaining scholarly inquiry and collective discussion.

Indeed, as the Royal Society notes in its reflections on the culture of science, “simply relying on the science of others is not an option. The greater the strength of the home science base, the greater its capacity to absorb and benefit from science done elsewhere” (Royal Society, 2012, p.17). Doctoral research embodies this ethos particularly clearly: it is a phase where scholars learn to formulate problems, design investigations, and situate their work within broader intellectual conversations but also in connection with local territories, displaying social and political commitment.

Beyond an Evolving Research Agenda

Taken together, the projects in this BoA outline an emerging research agenda concerned with the future of education in conditions of complexity. Mirroring the two Curricula (Pedagogical Research, and Education for Sustainability and Well-being) the studies explore how educational systems respond to technological transformations, and evolving professional practices, with high sensibility and focus towards inclusion and social justice. They also demonstrate the importance of interdisciplinary dialogue between pedagogical theory, sociology of education, community studies, and digital learning research.

At the same time, the research landscape presented here should not be understood as fixed. This is something we really want to emphasise to these young scholars: *don't be afraid of displaying themes and frameworks that are a snapshot of an evolving intellectual process*. As the doctoral projects develop, new connections may emerge between the areas currently identified, and additional questions may come to the fore.

In this sense, the present collection is less a final map than an initial cartography of a research terrain still under exploration.

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Access, Belonging, and Opportunity in Italian Doctoral Education: A Multiple Case Study

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Abstract

Internationalisation has increased the presence of international PhD candidates in Italian doctoral programmes, but recognition is not evenly distributed. What often matters is how programmes translate apparently neutral expectations into everyday judgements about competence, fit, and readiness. This study examines the moments where these judgements become consequential, including supervision, progress reviews, and the viva, and it also considers the opportunity structures that shape doctoral journeys, such as access to projects, paid roles, research networks, and fieldwork. The analysis draws on Bourdieu (1986) to describe how the doctoral field defines what counts and how resources are converted into legitimate advantage. It uses the Critical Race Theory to examine how appeals to neutrality and merit can still reproduce racialised and nationalised hierarchies of credibility and belonging (Delgado and Stefancic, 2017). It also mobilises Community Cultural Wealth (CCW) to attend to the resources candidates bring and develop, including linguistic, navigational, social, and resistant forms of capital, and to ask when these are recognised by institutions and when they are treated as irrelevant or problematic (Yosso, 2005). The project uses a qualitative multiple case embedded design (Yin, 2018) across two sites, the University of Padua and the University of Bologna, and three national origin cases, Pakistan, Iran, and Brazil. Evidence comes from semi-structured interviews with candidates and supervisors, alongside documentary analysis of programme and assessment materials. The aim is to identify mechanisms that shape unequal outcomes and to support feasible changes that strengthen fairness and belonging without lowering academic standards.

Keywords: *International PhD candidates, Italian doctoral programmes; Internationalisation; Multiple-case study*

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How do contemporary picturebooks from European borderlands (2015–2025) function as cultural practices to construct Critical Hope amidst the poly-crisis?

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Abstract

Originating from a phenomenological observation within a Kyiv air raid shelter, this doctoral research investigates the ontological transformation of the picturebook in the European borderlands between 2015 and 2025. The study posits that under the pressure of geopolitical poly-crisis, children's literature has evolved from a recreational object into a cultural technology of hope (McAdam et al., 2020). This concept functions as a critical survival mechanism that converts systemic uncertainty into micro-possibilities. By delineating a research matrix of fourteen nations, the inquiry redefines the border not merely as an administrative demarcation but as a shared emotional ecology shaped by conflict and displacement.

Theoretically, the project challenges the Romantic paradigm of the "hidden adult" (Nodelman, 2008) and argues that the protective insulation of childhood is no longer tenable in this region. Instead, it traces the emergence of the child as a competent witness (Murriss, 2016). To operationalize this shift, the research introduces a novel Four Ps Framework comprising Philosophy, Psychology, Pedagogy, and Politics. This matrix deconstructs how narratives nurture existential possibility, construct psychological agency, invite participatory meaning-making, and sustain the political capacity to aspire. Consequently, this framework serves as the primary instrument to distinguish critical hope from naive optimism.

Methodologically, the study employs an innovative triangulation strategy. It integrates the distant reading of macroscopic patterns from the International Youth Library corpus with the deep multimodal analysis of specific outliers. Crucially, this analysis extends to the materiality of the book itself (García-González & Deszcz-Tryhubczak, 2020) by examining how physical formats serve as geopolitical metaphors. For instance, it analyzes whether the protective weight of a hardback or the mobility of a paperback reflects distinct survival strategies. By synthesizing these textual analyses with creator interviews, the research aims to establish the Borderland Hope Model. This theoretical contribution demonstrates how visual culture functions as a cognitive field for reconstructing the subjecthood of the child amidst the ruins of the old world.

Keywords: *Picturebook, Multimodal Research, Hope Education, Children's Literature*

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GenAI-powered Personalized Learning Effectiveness within Blended Corporate Medical Device Training: A Mixed Methods Modelling Framework

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Abstract

Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) is increasingly positioned as a key enabler of Personalized Learning (PL), contributing to learning effectiveness by adapting content, feedback, and learning pathways to individual learner needs (Sharma & Kumar, 2024). Its growing implementation within organizational learning strategies introduces industry-specific challenges (Warg et al., 2024), particularly regarding its integration into Blended Learning (BL) environments (Park and Doo, 2024). A systematic literature review conducted in this study specifically highlights the underrepresentation of psychomotor knowledge acquisition within research on GenAI-supported PL, such as in hands-on medical device training (MDT). Since effective MDT requires a meaningful integration of physical practice with digital learning components (Grundgeiger et al., 2023), the medical device industry represents a relevant empirical context and one of the principal beneficiaries of addressing this gap.

This sequential mixed-methods study aims to develop and validate a comprehensive model of learning effectiveness factors for GenAI-powered PL strategies within blended corporate MDT. The objective of Phase I is to identify contextual effectiveness factors through interviews with educators and GenAI-based learning solution providers in the medical device industry, which are subsequently validated in Phase II via a large-scale survey analysis across Europe. Phase III aims to synthesize the findings into a theoretical model to derive practice recommendations for blended and medical device centered training curricula, aimed at enhancing learning effectiveness through GenAI-powered personalization.

Grounded in constructivist learning theory, this research seeks to advance evidence-based understanding of how GenAI can personalize BL approaches in corporate MDT, responding to calls for context-specific pedagogical effectiveness research about GenAI-enhanced PL in BL settings aligned with organizational learning objectives (Tu et al., 2025; Wu et al. 2025; Preechasin 2024). Empirical data collection is forthcoming as part of the ongoing doctoral research project.

Key words: *Generative Artificial Intelligence, Personalized Learning, Learning Effectiveness, Blended Learning, Organizational Learning, Medical Device Training*

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Social Justice and Educational Pathways: An interpretative qualitative study on the educational pathways of young adults with a migrant background in Veneto, Italy.

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Abstract

This research project focuses on the educational path of people with a migrant background in the Veneto region, Italy. The phenomenon of interest being explored is related to the meanings and interpretations that the latter attribute to their educational path, with a focus on the integration process and key turning points. The research questions are therefore as follows:

R1: How do young adults with a migrant background interpret their schooling experience in Veneto ex post?

R2: What meanings do young adults with a migrant background who were educated in Veneto attribute to the role of school in their *integration* process?

R3: What events or conditions had a decisive impact (turning points, if any) on the integration trajectories of young people with a migrant background?

The theoretical framework is provided by Social Justice Education (SJE), which promotes a critical approach through an interdisciplinary, intercultural and intersectional perspective. As this is an interpretative qualitative study, the research methods are linked to the semi-structured interviews in order to analyse in depth the interpretation by young people with a migrant background of their educational trajectories. In addition, several focus groups are planned with the aim of delving deeper into the issues brought up by shifting from individual narratives to a collective dialogical dimension. The research draws on guidelines regarding epistemological and ethical matters concerning interviewing found in the literature, including the stages of an interview investigation (Brinkmann & Kvale, 2015; Corbetta, 1999). The analysis of the collected data will be carried out according to the Reflexive Thematic Analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) following the steps outlined therein: familiarizing yourself with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing potential themes, defining and naming themes, writing up (Sirwan et al., 2025).

Key words: *Social Justice Education, Critical Pedagogy, Educational Trajectories, Adults with Migrant Background*

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Developing Technological Teacher Identity: A Mixed-Methods Intervention Embedded In Pre-Service Practicum

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Abstract.

This doctoral project addresses a central blind spot in research on educational technologies: the tendency to frame teachers' engagement with technology primarily in terms of competences (Redecker, 2017), while marginalising questions of professional identity (Beauchamp & Thomas, 2009), agency (Biesta & Tedder, 2006), and positioning (Akkerman & Meijer, 2011). Building on research on teacher professional identity (Akkerman & Meijer, 2011), this study conceptualises Technological Teacher Identity (TechID) as a dynamic and relational identity dimension that emerges through practice, discourse, and narrative positioning within socio-technical and postdigital educational contexts.

Drawing on dialogical (Akkerman & Meijer, 2011), sociomaterial (Orlikowski, 2007), and postdigital (Jandrić et al., 2018) perspectives, the project theorises TechID as neither a stable trait nor a set of skills (Sachs, 2005), but as an identity layer shaped by ongoing negotiations between individual trajectories (Lasky, 2005), institutional arrangements (Trevisan, 2024), and dominant narratives (Akkerman & Meijer, 2011) surrounding educational technology. Particular attention is given to identity-related mechanisms such as professional agency (Eteläpelto et al., 2013), reflexivity (Kelchtermans, 2009), social recognition (Gee, 2000), and narrative re-positioning (Søreide, 2006), which are often acknowledged in the literature but rarely operationalised within empirical research designs (Zeng & Liu, 2024).

On this theoretical basis, the project explores the possibility of intentionally supporting selected aspects of TechID through a formative intervention embedded in the university-based internship of pre-service primary teachers. Empirically, the study adopts a mixed-methods approach (Creswell, 2014) to examine identity-related changes and meaning-making processes across quantitative, qualitative, and relational data. By foregrounding the theoretical development and partial operationalisation of TechID, the project aims to contribute to current debates on teacher identity in postdigital education and to inform the pedagogical re-conceptualisation of practicum spaces as sites of intentional identity work.

Keywords: *Teacher Professional Identity, Agency, Positioning, Postdigital Education, Pre-service Teacher Education*

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Shaping the Future of Inclusive Education: A Study on Pre-Service Teachers' Intention to Teach in Inclusive Classrooms

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Abstract

Inclusive Education has become a global priority. However, preparing teachers to teach in inclusive classrooms is widely recognised as a central concern (Forlin, 2013). Guided by the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991), this ongoing mixed-method study explores pre-service teachers' intentions to teach in inclusive classrooms, with particular attention to the roles of attitudes towards inclusion, self-efficacy for inclusive teaching and concerns related to inclusive practice. The study is situated in Italy, one of the first European countries to institutionalise inclusive education, and whose school context is regarded as among the most inclusive in Europe (Sharma et al., 2018).

A concurrent mixed-method design has been adopted. Quantitative data are collected through a structured questionnaire administered to pre-service primary teachers enrolled in the third year of single-cycle master's degree in primary education sciences in University of Padova. The survey measures attitudes, self-efficacy, concerns, and intentions related to inclusive education, alongside background variables. At the current stage, exploratory and descriptive analyses have been conducted on the data collected to identify emerging patterns and trends. Qualitative data will be collected through semi-structured interviews.

Preliminary exploratory findings suggest that pre-service teachers report very high attitudes towards inclusion and high intentions to teach in inclusive classrooms, alongside relatively high levels of self-efficacy. Nevertheless, certain concerns, particularly those related to resources and acceptance (difficulties), remain evident, though at lower levels. These early findings indicate that positive attitudes do not necessarily eliminate concerns, highlighting the complexity of pre-service teachers' preparedness for inclusive education. Final analyses will be conducted once data collection is complete, intending to provide a holistic understanding of the factors shaping intentions to teach inclusively.

Key words: *Inclusive Education, Theory of Planned Behaviour, Attitude, Teacher Self-efficacy, Concern, Intention, Pre-service Teacher*

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Early leaving from education and training and the promotion of educating community systems: approaches, methods and tools of second-chance schools between institutions and territory

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Abstract

To cope with the growing number of students at risk of dropping out of school and experiencing educational poverty, Second Chance Schools (SSOs) provide environments that actively combat inequality, promoting knowledge, educational justice, equity and democracy while supporting those in difficult situations. Promoted by the European Union as early as 1995, SSOs have since been supported by European and national educational strategies and policies, they target adolescents and young people at risk of early school leaving, which can have significant social, cultural, personal and professional consequences.

This doctoral research focuses on early school leaving, examining the role of SSOs and the educational community in promoting the educational and training success of young people who leave school prematurely. Particular attention is given to European contexts, specifically Italy and Spain. Adopting a pedagogical perspective the research will investigate the educational practices, territorial networks and visions of adolescence that characterise these alternative educational contexts. The objective is to identify good pedagogical practices within these European contexts that can inform the design of interventions to combat or prevent early school leaving.

Methodologically, a mixed-methods approach will be employed to combine quantitative and qualitative analyses, offering a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon and the effectiveness of Second Chance Schools. Using a variety of qualitative and quantitative research tools will highlight the structural, organisational, pedagogical and educational dimensions that emerge from the daily experience of the studied contexts.

Key words: *Second Chance Schools, Early School Leaving, Adolescence, Educational Community, Mixed-methods Research*

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Improving soft skills: a research project on expression and self-assessment in Professional Education students

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Abstract

Contemporary Western society is characterised by economic uncertainty, labour instability and fragile social ties. These conditions profoundly affect the identity development of young adults and their transition into professional life (Bauman et al., 2011; Arnett, 2004; Marani, 2014; Rosci, 2022). In this context, higher education, particularly in the helping professions, must do more than simply impart disciplinary knowledge; it must also intentionally foster the development of soft skills to prepare students for the challenges they will face in life and work (Grant et al., 2023; Verkooijen et al., 2024; King et al., 2025).

This study aims to design and implement a workshop-based educational programme for second- and third-year Professional Education students at six universities: Padova, Udine, Trento, Bologna, Firenze and Brescia. The pathway is intended to support the development and expression of soft skills, while improving students' capacity for self-assessment. More broadly, the educational pathway seeks to provide a formative experience that fosters human and professional growth and equips students to handle the complexity, uncertainty and relational demands of professional practice.

Adopting an educational action research design grounded in a critical-emancipatory paradigm, this study not only seeks to understand educational processes, but also to transform them (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011; Giroux, 2020). The laboratory intervention comprises three workshops integrated with students' internship experiences, drawing on narrative tools, dialogic mediation, collaborative learning, problem-based learning and reflective practices.

A mixed-methods approach is employed, combining pre- and post-validated and unvalidated questionnaires (n = 161 pre; n = 122 post) with qualitative tools. These include 12 focus groups, 145 internship reflective diaries, 161 pre-internship and 123 post-internship self-assessment forms, 140 critical incidents and 123 photovoice contributions. The quantitative data will be analysed using SPSS, while the qualitative data will undergo thematic analysis and Situational Analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2021).

Keywords: *Soft Skills, Young Adults, University Students, Personal Identity, Professional Identity*

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Sympathetic Inks: New connections among knowledge systems, institutions, and local contexts to reframe educational communities

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Abstract

This study examines the transformation of educational services through the integration of Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory (1979), the Capability Approach (Sen, 1999; Nussbaum, 2011), and the Social Innovation Paradigm (Moulaert et al., 2013). The research explores the conditions under which educational management can foster collective well-being, beginning with a preliminary investigation into the capabilities emerging from the University's founding documents and institutional values. Utilizing Participatory Action Research (PAR) (Reason & Bradbury, 2008), the study analyses the convergence between these academic premises and the community-based educational work, investigating how ecological university-territory collaborations can generate enabling opportunities for youth agency. The inquiry is driven by the specific experience of "Focus Giovani" in Vicenza: an innovative experimental collaboration between local educational entities and the public administration. In this model, competitive dynamics are replaced by a logic of cooperation and a convergence of objectives directed toward the shared goal of youth well-being. A subsequent phase of the research investigates how these institutional intents resonate with the narratives of young people—the primary recipients of the city's educational projects—regarding their own aspirations. This process documents their transition from passive recipients of institutional planning to active, participatory protagonists in co-designing their futures (Santos, 2014). From an ecosystemic perspective, the concluding phase involves university interns stationed within the same educational entities that comprise "Focus Giovani," conceptualizing them as vital connective elements that close the research circle. Within the framework of Gutierrez's (2008) "Third Space", these interns act as boundary-spanners who navigate and merge academic theory with field-based practice. Their privileged vantage point highlights not only the formative and relational opportunities of the internship but also provides a vital feedback loop to the University. This contribution reveals a critical need for Higher Education institutions to transcend their traditional boundaries and evolve toward a model of integrated knowledge fostered by a continuous, reciprocal exchange with the territory. As a prospective development, the study suggests a further evolution to substantiate the participants' voices through the creation of an Open Educational Resource (OER) (Wiley & Hilton, 2018) designed as a "Territorial Connectivity

Hub." This tool is envisioned as an infrastructure capable of sustaining interconnections between territorial entities, the University, and citizens, incentivizing mutual contamination through a live, "in vivo" exchange of experiences. In conclusion, this research contributes to the debate on social innovation and higher education by demonstrating that Universities can evolve from mere knowledge providers to become orchestrators of networked learning environments, where integrated knowledge is co-constructed to sustain long-term collective well-being.

Keywords: *University-Territory Connection, Youth Well-being, Capability Approach, Social Innovation, Community Empowerment*

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An exploratory study on the disaffection of future educators and trainers in contemporary complexity. A dialogue between youth from GenZ and university teachers

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Abstract

Through a critical analysis of current societal conditions, the study examines how universities have progressively incorporated market-oriented logics, reshaping educational practices, institutional expectations, and pedagogical relationships (Giroux, 2014; Busch, 2017; Biesta, 2023).

The literature describes the growing prevalence of existential distress among youths, expressed through phenomena such as eating disorders, social withdrawal, interpersonal violence, and addictive behaviours (WHO, 2025). These forms of malaise, often accompanied by disengagement from social and civic life (Baldacci, 2019), individualism and competitive behaviours (Han, 2024), suggest significant difficulties in the development of critical, reflective, and empathetic capacities. Such difficulties are further connected to a reconfiguration of educational relationships (Haidt, 2024), including those with teachers (Daliri-Ngametua et al., 2021) and parental figures (Rothwell, 2026), which affects students' engagement with learning and their ability to navigate the demands of contemporary society.

The primary aim of the study is to explore the motivations and conditions that contribute to attitudes of disaffection toward university life among students enrolled in the bachelor degree programmes in Educational Sciences of three Universities (Padua, IUSVE, Trieste). In addition, the project seeks to promote reflective self-awareness among students regarding the implications of disengagement for the construction of their professional and personal identities.

The research is grounded in the theoretical framework of critical-emancipatory pedagogy (Denzin et al., 2023) and employs a mixed-methods design (Tashakkori et al., 2021). Quantitative data are collected through validated questionnaires (n=580), while qualitative insights are generated via focus groups (FG) (n=4) with students and collective interviews (n=5) with teachers, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of student disaffection in higher education, while identifying pedagogical practices that may foster meaningful participation in academic life.

Keywords: *Disaffection; Critical Pedagogy; University Students-teachers Dialogue*

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Problematic Smartphone Use and Students' Performance; Pedagogical Approaches and Intervention Models for Prevention

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Abstract

The problematic use of technology and its products is increasing day by day that results in spending too much time on mobile screens affecting humans and becoming a concern globally, particularly among adolescents (Ertemel & Ari, 2020). PSU is defined as an inability to regulate one's use of the mobile phone, which eventually involves negative consequences in daily life (Billieux, 2012). It has been on the rise among university students globally (Boumosleh & Jaalouk, 2017). Excessive smartphone use had the primary negative consequences such as decreased academic productivity, poor physical health, compromised mental well-being, and decreased social interactions (Alotaibi et al., 2022). To reduce the negative effects of smartphone use, it is necessary to limit their use (Elamin et al., 2024). There are many research studies that have identified key aspects linking PSU to poor academic performance (Das & Chaliha, 2025); (Albursan et al., 2022), including reduced sleep quality, impaired attention, and decreased self-control as well as reduced physical activity (Meena et al., 2021); (Khan et al., 2024). Academic performance is also negatively impacted through reduced self-regulation, increased cognitive load, and classroom multi-tasking. The impact on mental health includes increased anxiety (Das & Chaliha, 2025) (Alhassan et al., 2025) depression (Alhassan et al., 2025), and stress (Das & Chaliha, 2025), alongside sleep disturbance (Elamin et al., 2024). Cognitive functions including working memory, attention, and concentration are negatively affected by excessive smartphone use (León Méndez et al., 2024); (Elamin et al., 2024). Various research studies exist on school-based smartphone addiction prevention programs; but there is a critical gap in evidence-based pedagogical interventions specifically designed for and tested within university academic contexts (Alhassan et al., 2025). Most intervention research targets middle and high school students, not university students whose developmental stage, learning autonomy, and smartphone use patterns differ significantly. Most intervention research occurs in single-site, single-culture studies, primarily in East Asian or North American contexts. In various countries significant variation exists in smartphone ownership, usage patterns, academic cultures, and psychological factors across different regions. Hence, the current research study explores the effects of problematic smartphone usage on university students' academic performance, health and physical activity as well as cognitive and psychological factors as an integrated approach by conducting the pedagogical intervention as a prevention strategy within specific geographical and

university contexts in Italy and Pakistan. For the pretest, through a structured questionnaire the researcher collected data from ninety students of Laurea Magistrale and Laurea Triennale each from the students at University of Padova, Italy and University of Malakand, Pakistan. The researcher found that in Pakistan, a total of forty-one students in Pakistan used their smartphones for more than five hours per day. In Italy, a total of thirty-three students in Italy used their smartphones for more than five hours per day. Then the researcher conducted a structured pedagogical intervention with these students in Italy through both online and in physical classes and will conduct it in Pakistan. After a month, the researcher will conduct a post test.

Keywords: *Problematic Smartphone Use, University Students, Pedagogical Intervention*

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Belonging in Intercultural Early Childhood Education: A Pedagogical Analysis of Educational Practices with Chinese Migrant Families

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Abstract

This presentation addresses a central question in intercultural pedagogy: how can early childhood education (ECE) institutions intentionally foster a sense of belonging among children from migrant families, rather than leaving integration to chance? Focusing on Chinese migrant families in Italy — the fourth-largest non-EU immigrant group (Ministero del Lavoro e delle Politiche Sociali, 2025) — the study pursues two interconnected aims: first, to develop a set of pedagogically grounded analytical categories for evaluating the quality of intercultural practices in ECE settings; second, to outline an empirical research design capable of testing these categories in concrete educational contexts. Theoretically, the paper reconceptualizes *belonging* (*sensu di appartenenza*), drawing on Baumeister and Leary's (1995) belongingness hypothesis and Xodo's (2003) framework of personal identity construction, not as a psychological state to be measured but as an intentional educational outcome shaped through symbolic, relational, and institutional mediation. Six analytical categories are proposed: educational recognition, symbolic and narrative mediation, active participation, the school–family alliance, teachers' professional reflexivity, and the school's proactive engagement with public space. The paper then reviews European and Italian policy frameworks (Council of Europe, 2008; Göregen et al., 2021), identifying a persistent gap between intercultural rhetoric and actual practice (Silva et al., 2020). To move beyond this gap, a qualitative multiple-case study design is proposed, encompassing three types of ECE settings in the Padua area — private Catholic schools (FISM), state schools, and Chinese community-run schools — using semi-structured interviews, participant observation, and document analysis. Methodologically, the study is guided by a non-essentialist "liquid interculturality" framework (Dervin, 2011; Holliday, 1999; Zilliacus et al., 2017), which treats culture as dynamically constructed in everyday interactions rather than as a fixed identity label. Chinese migrant families serve as a privileged heuristic lens, given the complex cultural negotiations involved: as Porcarelli and Liu (2025) demonstrate, despite theological divergences, Confucian ethics and Catholic pedagogy share a deep practical convergence in their emphasis on moral formation and the holistic development of the person — a convergence that renders Catholic FISM schools a particularly meaningful educational choice for many Chinese families in Italy. The study's findings carry broader relevance for inclusive ECE policy and practice in increasingly diverse societies.

Keywords: *Belonging, Intercultural Education, Early Childhood Education, Chinese Migrant Families*

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Reframing Assessment in Schools through “Students as Partners in Assessment”

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Abstract

Recent European surveys (TALIS, 2025) show the widespread use of observational practices and continuous feedback in assessment, while student involvement remains limited. International research (Black & Wiliam, 1998; Boud & Soler, 2016) suggests that assessment can be reconceptualised beyond summative and formative approaches as a shared, learning-oriented process through assessment for learning and sustainable assessment. In this view, participatory practices such as co-constructing criteria and using feedback for improvement are central to fostering students’ assessment literacy and lifelong competences.

Within this framework, the Students as Partners in Assessment (SaPA) approach positions teachers and students as co-actors in assessment processes, transforming evaluation into an opportunity for authentic learning and shared meaning-making (Ní Bheoláin et al., 2020; Nieminen et al., 2025). However, evidence from the Italian school context shows that student involvement remains marginal and discontinuous despite strong rhetorical commitments to formative assessment (Slaviero, Doria & Grion, 2025).

This doctoral research adopts a sequential design combining grounded theory and design-based research (Hoadley & Campos, 2022; Anderson & Shattuck, 2012) to investigate participatory assessment practices and assessment training in K–12 education, with a specific focus on SaPA. The study integrates three strands. The first analyses assessment practices in a stratified national sample of Italian schools (n = 696) through document analysis, questionnaires, and a qualitative case study. Results show that assessment is predominantly teacher-managed, framed through formative and summative lenses, and weakly participatory from the students’ perspective. A case study on narrative feedback highlights both its potential for enhancing student agency and tensions related to grading cultures.

The second strand updates an international systematic review on SaPA in schools (Nieminen et al., 2025), reconceptualising partnership as scaffolded student agency enacted through structured and dialogic processes. The third strand reviews teacher professional development models in assessment to inform the design of a self-managed professional learning environment focused on SaPA.

Overall, the study documents the persistent gap between formative assessment discourse and practice and proposes a research-informed pathway to support more participatory, sustainable, and learner-centred assessment cultures in schools.

Keywords: *Assessment Literacy; Peer Assessment; Secondary Education; Assessment as Learning*

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Peer feedback in early childhood education as a tool for developing teachers' educational practices

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Abstract

Feedback is a concept that has been widely studied in higher and university education, particularly in relation to peer assessment (Castoldi, 2012; Grion & Serbati, 2018; Nigris & Agrusti, 2021). It provides students with information about their level of performance and encourages them to self-correct in order to reach new standards (Hattie & Timperley, 2007; Boud & Molloy, 2013). According to Vygotsky (1978), social support is fundamental to cognitive development and represents a resource for lifelong learning. Although extensively studied, research on the role of feedback in preschool contexts remains limited. The present qualitative study (Lincoln & Guba, 2000) is framed within a socio-constructivist paradigm (Vygotsky, 1978; Bruner, 1996). The research adopts a multi-method approach, integrating qualitative and quantitative techniques (Roller & Lavrakas, 2015). It is structured in two phases: exploratory and empirical.

The exploratory phase involved a systematic review of the literature on peer feedback in preschool education (Zoroaster & Restiglian, 2025b), aimed both at identifying existing studies and at examining whether useful tools were available for detecting peer feedback in this age group. The empirical phase, divided into three strands, included an ethnographic case study (Merriam, 1988; Benvenuto, 2015; Fusch et al., 2017) conducted in five nursery schools (Veneto and the United Kingdom), aimed at identifying peer feedback through video recordings, participant observations, and an observation protocol specifically designed for the study. The analysis identified 851 communicative segments, 661 of which were feedback instances, introducing a new category “relational feedback” and distinguishing between direct/indirect and explicit/implicit feedback (Zoroaster & Restiglian, 2025a). The second strand involved semi-structured interviews with teachers to explore their knowledge of peer feedback and to develop a definition appropriate to the preschool context. The findings show that most teachers do not mention it spontaneously, but acknowledge its importance when prompted. The third strand, currently ongoing, involves a questionnaire designed to investigate knowledge and practices among a larger sample of preschool teachers.

Preliminary results of the project suggest the need for educational environments that foster interaction and peer feedback, supported by open and dialogic educational styles. The study contributes to raising awareness of the role of feedback and observation in preschool educational practice.

Keywords: *Peer Feedback; Early Childhood Education; Preschool Learning; Teacher Practices*

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